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Prevent and Control Gray Mold in the Plant

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ABSTRACT

Botrytis cinerea is a fungus that causes a huge loss of crop production. There is no specific permanent solution for this problem. With various side effects, there are few techniques for reducing this problem. Among all the solutions, chemical fungicide is the main solution for getting rid of this destroyer with a huge side effect. The new approach, transgenic plant production, is a new and effective method compared to any other. This study will focus on the best and most useful properties of transgenic plants compared with other fungicides.

Keywords

Botrytis cinerea; Gray mold; Fungicide; Bio-control; RNA interference; Transgenic plant.

Introduction

Gray mold is scientifically known as *Botrytis cinerea* which is a plant attacking airborne pathogen with necrotrophic pathogenicity, which causes full distraction of plant attacking over 200 crop hosts Williamson B et al.2007 [1]. It is recognized worldwide as the second most dangerous fungal strain that highly affects agricultural production and economical statistics Guo Q et al. 2016 [2].

Because of having a variety of attacking modes, changeable inoculum sources, and the surviving ability as mycelia or conidia or for extended periods as sclerotia in field dust, gray mold contamination is difficult to control and quite impossible to eliminate properly Williamson B et al. 2007 [1]. Various strategies like essential oils, plant extracts, inorganic chemicals, biocontrol, defense activators, hot water treatments, fresh air supply, and modified storage conditions have been tested to reduce losses from gray mold Krasnow C et al.2022 [3].

The economic losses through *B. cinerea* easily exceed \$10 billion worldwide Dartanhã J et al.2012[4]. The gray mold's suitable environments are with moderate temperatures ranging between 15~25°C. However, it can even survive under freezing temperatures at 0°C, making it a serious threat to storehouses and greenhouse gases Guo Q et al. 2016 [2].

The affection initiates with spore deposition on the surface of the host plant through penetration and then colonization of the host tissues. The conidia became the main inoculum source for new infection sites after the first colonization of the fungus go through under suitable conditions, start sporulation profusely on the dead tissues [Hammond SM et al.2001](#) [5].

Two catalytic subunits, BcNoxA and BcNoxB, contain by gray mold, are mainly responsible for pathogenicity and sclerotia formation of sclerotia, overall that allow the fungi to survive under suitable and non-suitable conditions environmental conditions, and these are also very important for sexual reproduction [Dartanhã J et al. 2012](#) [4] [Al-Masri M et al. 2005](#) [6]. The protection of crops against gray mold is mainly based on chemical fungicides [Brito C et al. 2021](#) [7]. Nowadays, many gene silencing-based fungicides are also on the market. Plants get some of their innate immunity against gray mold and other fungicides [Jani kelloniemi et al .2022](#) [8]. The plant's defense mechanism is also important for plant protection [Islam A et al .2006](#) [9].

Crops' innate defense response to *Botrytis cinerea* is a complex biological process involving changes at the molecular (i.e., transcriptional), physiological, and biochemical levels. After recognizing a pathogen, signaling molecule and cascade initiate resistance activity by balancing hormonal signaling pathways, and thus, defense occurs [Synan Abu Qamar et al.2022](#)[10]. This study will focus on the best way to find the control of gray mold pathogenicity.

With significant efficiency, chemical fungicides have been used to control plant diseases with both pre-and post-harvest treatment against the decay of fruits and crops. It is not a proper solution among any of them [Guo Q et al. 2016](#) [2]. But nowadays, there are also a few genetically modified techniques, mainly RNA silencing mechanisms, and host-specific fungicides are available. Chemicals that are not harmful to the environment and animals are also on the market. Research is also focused on natural defense mechanisms of the plant by innate immunity, recognition of the molecular pattern of fungus and other non-sense RNA in the RNA pool of host cell is the main basis. Also, the fresh air technique (mainly for greenhouse plants) is preferable for many farmers.

Control by chemical and limitation of chemical resistance.

From the beginning, chemical fungicides are the main solution to get rid of gray mold [4]. The enormous consumption of chemical fungicides is associated with a huge bad impact on the ecosystem and animal health [11]. The side effect is clear nowadays to everyone depending on chemicals in farming. Because of minimum impacts on the environment and human health of several site-specific fungicides targeting *Botrytis* spp, the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) declare them as "reduced-risk" fungicides, showing less possibility of contamination of groundwater and pest resistance along with their consistency with the principles of integrated pest management[2].

Some of the main and major chemicals used are phenylpyrroles, fenhexamid, phenylpyrroles, etc [12]. But it contains many histological effects on the animal body like histological alterations [13] Methylglyoxal stress, and alter hybrid histidine kinase activity [14]. There are mainly five types of fungicides based on action methodologies, like respiration and osmoregulation, microtubule assembly, and sterol biosynthesis. That action can be reversed by methionine [8]. Among all these types of fungicides affecting gray mold, respiratory-inhibiting fungicides are the mainly consumed chemicals for the defense of crops from gray mold disease, which showed inhibitory activity for the fungal development by disrupting the mitochondrial respiration at the ubiquinol oxidation center (Q_o) site and reduction of the reactive rate of a succinate-dehydrogenase enzyme that situates in the inner membrane of eukaryotic mitochondria[2].

The respiration process in mitochondria conserves energy by linking NADH oxidation and electron-coupled proton translocation by ATP synthesis through a central pathway that involves three large protein complexes. Strobilurin fungicides block electron flow through one of these complexes and disrupt energy flow[15].

Fig 1.1: Complex III has two Quinone binding sites, Q_o and Q_i, from their relative positions in the inner mitochondrial membrane. At Q_o, ubiquinol is oxidized by a cascade of one electron to the adjacent rieske Fe/S center and the other to cytochrome bL. At the same time, at Q_i, ubiquinone is reduced in one-electron steps by cytochrome bc. Strobilurins inhibit electron cascade to cytochrome b of mitochondrial complex III. G143A mutation is the principal resistance to strobilurins [16] [2].

Fig 1.2: Carboxamide inhibits dehydrogenase, which plays two roles in respiration Complex II by catalyzing the oxidation of succinate to fumarate in the mitochondrial Krebs cycle and transferring electrons from succinate to ubiquinone in the mitochondrial electron transport chain.

Using extreme fungi-side making gray mold resistant to chemicals. The evolution of fungicide resistance has become a major problem worldwide, particularly in cases where high resistance factors have been reported and the frequencies of mutant phenotypes in the population are high. This phenomenon may greatly decrease the efficacy of the active ingredients concerned, increasing the cost of chemical control and potentially resulting in damage to the environment if repeated treatment is required [16]. Because of the huge range of pathogenic strains having resistance against fungicides, it's now suitable to apply fungicides that can target multiple sites rather than the site-specific ones.

Multiple-site affecting fungicides such as captan and thiram has been used to inhibit the respiration process on fungus and for the ability to target various chemical pathways. These could show significant activity in suppressing the fungal growth and disease development within the pathogen by targeting some thiol-containing enzymes, which can deduct the rate of fungal conidial formation. But after all, it showed weak effectiveness against the mycelial development of pathogenic fungus[16]. However, the last two decades have witnessed the evolutionary development of site-specific fungicides targeting gray mold. They can maintain their effectiveness against gray mold disease by applying in minimum doses[16].

Biological Control and limitation.

Bio-control of the high humidity-promoted *Botrytis cinerea* is mainly based on saprophytes[17]. Biological control against gray mold has been attempted by many microbes like *Trichoderma*, *Serratia mar-crescent*, *Gliocladium rodeo*, *Penicillium* sp., and *Bacillus circulans* [18]. Using biological organisms has many reports of inhibition of infection through nutritional competition between microorganisms. Species of leaf-based bacteria yeasts and filamentous fungi can inhibit pathogens by competing for nutrients. Mycoparasitism of fungi by filamentous fungi has been recorded in many systems. Parasitism and antibiosis are also related to a few bacteria. *Bacillus licheniformis* reduced gray mold on tomato plants and flowers, and *Trichoderma harzianum* significantly reduced *B. cinerea* development on beans. Other microbial species such as *Bacillus subtilis*, *Rhodosporidium paludigenum*, and *Pichia guilliermondii* have control against *Botrytis* fruit rot of tomato[7].

It has been related to many bacterial strains, but antibiotic production by fungi and yeasts has also been mentioned [19]. However, the result of antagonistic yeasts is not as functional as fungicides and usually needs to combine fungicides or other factors substances to gain a good result. Much work has shown that antagonistic yeasts combined with calcium chloride, salicylic acid, sodium bicarbonate, silicon, boron, and glycine betaine can significantly improve their bio-control efficacy in the control of post-harvest diseases in various fruits.

A combination of hot water treatment with *Candida guilliermondii* or *Pichia membranaefaciens* showed better control efficacy against *B. cinerea* in tomato fruit [4].

The scarcity of biocontrol systems depends on many reasons, of which the following are the most important: Ayub et al. 2018 [19]

- Easy accessibility of cheap and effective chemical fungicides can easily be applied on the field.
- Surface conditions of plant areal portion do not suit the survival and activity of bio-control methods dependent on microorganisms.
- A few biocontrol systems are less effective than potent chemicals; their effectiveness is not always consistent; they control a narrow spectrum of diseases.
- Biocontrol formula and its distribution are comparatively more difficult than for chemicals one.

Biological Control with participation in RNA interference (Mechanism of RNA silencing between plants and Eukaryotic).

In plants, the gene silencing technique depends on two procedures: transcriptional gene silencing (TGS) and the second is post-transcriptional gene silencing (PTGS). TGS suppresses the transcription process through the methylation of the 5' untranslated region. On the contrary, PTGS causes the methylation of a coding region to occur transcript degradation[20]. TGS is a nuclear-localized procedure that binds transcriptional machinery and quenches transcription by inhabiting a promoter region. Different methods of TGS are; RNA-directed DNA methylation (RdDM), genomic imprinting, paramutation, transposon silencing, transgene silencing, and position effect.

TGS is predominantly responsible for transposon and transgene silencing, but unlike TGS, PTGS plays a limited role in this silencing. Post-transcriptional gene silencing is a cytoplasm-localized to target and damage mRNA transcripts of fundamental genes. Different methods of PTGS are RNA interference (RNAi), clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats[21].

Recently, the exogenous application of double-stranded RNA (dsRNA-), small interfering RNA (siRNA-), and hpRNA-mediated post-transcriptional gene silencing (i.e., RNA interference or gene silencing) has emerged as a promising strategy in enhancing plant resistance against phytopathogenic diseases[22]. *B. cinerea* DCL1 and DCL2 proteins synthesize and deliver siRNA to host plant cells to interfere with the host RNAi machinery AGO1 and subsequently silences suppress the host species' immune response[22].

Plant immune response to infection with RNA.

Host-induced gene silencing (HIGS) is one of the methods that have been used to enhance resistance against *B. cinerea* by expressing dsRNAs that target essential fungal genes in host plant species leading to disease

resistance[22]. *Botrytis cinerea*'s small RNA (sRNA) effectors modulate the plant immune system to induce gray mold disease[22].

The HIGS can achieve durable resistance; however, due to the lack of a stable genetic transformations system for several economically important crops, the costs associated with development, registration, and maintenance of the genetically modified crops, as well as the challenges related to the public acceptance of these plants, utilization of HIGS as a disease management strategy against *B. cinerea* is not currently attainable. Two main defense pathways govern a plant's innate immunity. The first one is PAMP or pathogen-associated molecular pattern mainly based on recognition of damage-associated molecular patterns containing specific receptors. And the second one is the effector-triggered immunity, also known as ETI. Both PTI and ETI signaling lead to a large number of transcriptome reprogramming. Hormones like salicylate, jasmonate, and ethylene take part in defense responses. SA signaling is based on defense against biotrophs, and JA and ET Pathways are against necrotrophy[8].

Production of transgenic plants for inhibition of gray mold.

Transgenic plants have been produced by inserting antifungal genes to confer resistance against fungal pathogens. Overall, transgenic approaches can be distributed in various categories[9].

- Over-expression of directly pathogen toxic genes that produce compounds like (PR proteins) and phytoalexins, peroxidase, and lignin reduces their growth[9]. The mode of action of phytoalexins on fungi includes cytoplasmic granulation, disorganization of cellular contents, rupture of the plasma membrane, and inhibition of fungal enzymes, leading to the inhibition of spore germination and germ tube elongation and the reduction or inhibition of mycelial growth [23]. PRs are induced in the host cell in response to infection or abiotic stimuli, and their accumulation forms an integral component of innate immune responses in plants[23].
- Expression of genes of fundamental chemicals, e.g., hydrogen peroxidase (H₂O₂), salicylic acid (SA), Jasmonate(JA), and ethylene (C₂H₄) that regulate signals to initiate plant defenses[9]. This also includes the innate immunity of plant defense mechanisms [8]. SA biosynthesis requires the EDS1 and PAD4 genes, whereas the EDS5 and SID2 genes regulate SA biosynthesis[24]. NPR1 is a transcriptional coregulator, acts downstream of SA, and plays an essential role in SA-dependent defense signaling pathways. Mutations in the NPR1 gene cause impaired SA-induced transcriptional reprogramming and establishment of SAR and enhanced HR (Hormonal Regulation)[25].NPR1 promotes physical interaction between NPR1 and a transcription factor TGA3 or GRX480 to activate the expression of defense genes [23,25].

Fig 2: SA pathway is critical and much important for innate immunity. Many plants like grapevine produce the SA pathway. PAMP (pathogen-associated molecular pattern) and ETI (Effector trigger immunity). Both contain SA dependency for proper immunity.

Fig 3: Jasmonic acid (JA) signaling cascade plays a vital role in plant defenses against necrotrophic pathogens and herbivorous insects afflicting roots and shoots. This pathway is also activated by interacting with beneficial systemic resistance-induced microbes. Stresses induce the synthesis of JA, which can be converted through JAR1 to JA-Ile, which is biologically active. JA-Ile active JA-responsive genes by releasing the MYC2 transcription factor from the JAZ–MYC2 complex [26]. Then through SA responsive genes, defense initiate[11].

- Suspend of fungal toxins, thus stopping the invasion of the fungus through the expression of the R gene.
- Other methods are the production of RNAi, RNase, and lysozyme. In such cases, genes isolated from sources apart from plants are exploited. Reports also include the introduction of double-stranded RNA from fungal affecting virus and lysozymes genes cloned from human tissues[9].

Conclusion

Because of the various action moods, gray mold is a big thread for all crop species. Chemical fungicides contain a specific mood of action, which is beneficial for a certain period after pathogens get resistant and the fungicide becomes inactive. Biological living animals are a competitor of pathogens and protect against pathogens having themselves more active, which sometimes cause harm to the environment as well as consumers. Having a strong bacterial colony is never a good expectation. Bacteria get resistant to arsenic cadmium and other metabolic reactions. Next-generation fungicides (RNA-based) are not very handy and uncomfortable to use. Having naked RNA in the environment is always controversial. Despite having some side effects, transgenic plants are the best way to eliminate the gray mold issue. Innate immunity comprises the most specific and contains various moods of action and a proper inactivation of affecting pathogen. Only a transgenic plant contains a better and more accurate solution. If further research accelerates may be affecting pathogen could be a source of energy and protein complementary for the plant itself. Nowadays, transgenic plants could be a great solution for the balanced agro environment and a green production policy.

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